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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL STIGMA ON THE PSYCHO-EMOTIONAL STATE OF WOMEN EXPERIENCED IN DOMESTIC VIOLENCE

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Abstract: This article analyzes the impact of social stigma on the psycho-emotional state of women exposed to domestic violence from a socio-psychological perspective. It emphasizes how stereotypes, social pressure, and processes of stigmatization within society lead to anxiety, depression, low self-esteem, and social withdrawal among women. The role of social support networks, local communities, and social institutions is considered an important protective factor.

Key words: domestic violence, social stigma, psycho-emotional state, women's psychology, social pressure, stereotypes, depression, anxiety.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada oilaviy zo'ravonlikka duchor bo'lgan ayollarning psixo-emotsional holatiga ijtimoiy stigma ta'siri ijtimoiy-psixologik yondashuv asosida tahlil qilinadi. Jamiyatdagi stereotiplar, ijtimoiy bosim va stigmatizatsiya jarayonlari ayollarda xavotir, depressiya, o'z-o'zini past baholash hamda ijtimoiy chekinish holatlarining kuchayishiga olib kelishi yoritib beriladi. Shuningdek, ijtimoiy qo'llab-quvvatlash tizimi, mahalla muhiti va ijtimoiy institutlarning himoya omili sifatidagi roli asoslab beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: oilaviy zo'ravonlik, ijtimoiy stigma, psixo-emotsional holat, ayollar psixologiyasi, ijtimoiy bosim, stereotiplar, depressiya, xavotir.

Аннотация: В статье с социально-психологической точки зрения анализируется влияние социальной стигмы на психоэмоциональное состояние женщин, подвергшихся домашнему насилию. Показано, что общественные стереотипы, социальное давление и процессы стигматизации способствуют развитию тревожности, депрессии, заниженной самооценки и социальной изоляции у женщин. Обоснована роль социальной поддержки, местного сообщества и социальных институтов как значимых защитных факторов.

Ключевые слова: домашнее насилие, социальная стигма, психоэмоциональное состояние, психология женщин, социальное давление, стереотипы, депрессия, тревожность.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the problem of domestic violence has been recognized as a pressing socio-psychological issue on a global scale. In particular, violence against women has not only physical but also profound psychological and social consequences. According to the World Health Organization, a large proportion of women experience domestic violence at least once in their lives. This situation leads to a decline in women's mental health, social activity, and overall quality of life. The problems faced by women who have experienced domestic violence are not limited to the act of violence itself. Social stigma existing in society—namely negative attitudes toward the victim, blame, discrimination, and exclusion—further aggravates their psycho-emotional state. In many societies, domestic violence is perceived as a private matter, and the victim is often interpreted as the culprit. This perception leads women to refrain from seeking help, conceal the problem, and remain under constant psychological pressure. Social stigma intensifies feelings of shame, fear, low self-esteem, social withdrawal, and loneliness.

Psychological studies indicate that stigmatization repeatedly activates traumatic experiences, contributing to the development of chronic stress, depressive states, and post-traumatic stress disorder. Therefore, the problem of domestic violence should be examined not only from legal or medical perspectives but also from a socio-psychological standpoint. In Uzbekistan, combating violence against women is one of the key directions of state policy. Laws and social programs adopted at the initiative of the President are aimed at protecting women and ensuring their legal and psychological safety. However, stereotypes and mechanisms of stigmatization that persist in public consciousness continue to hinder the complete resolution of this problem.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The negative psychological consequences of domestic violence include emotional restraint, negativism, refusal to express one's position, a tendency toward self-sacrifice, fear of expressing the need for love and close communication, and persistent negative experiences. These manifestations are associated with deformation of the emotional sphere, which contributes to the suppression of emotional expression. Among the consequences of domestic violence are also symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder. Numerous studies conducted in recent years indicate that psychological violence within the family is most clearly manifested in combination with physical and emotional abuse. Even after psychological violence, the victimized woman is often unable to fully return to normal living conditions. This is explained by several factors. Having lived under constant control for an extended period, she may lose many social contacts due to limited decision-making skills and excessive dependence. Women who have experienced domestic violence often demonstrate difficulties in communication and social interaction. They are characterized by heightened anxiety, dependence on their partner, low self-esteem, feelings of inadequacy, a high level of self-criticism, and a tendency to blame themselves for the situation. Compared with women who have not been victims of violence, they exhibit significant differences in levels of subjective control.

The most dangerous form of domestic violence is psychological or emotional abuse. Psychological violence undermines family stability and negatively affects the mental health of family members, often leading to psychological trauma. Threats, insults, and emotionally expressed bullying represent elementary forms of psychological violence within the family. This form of violence occurs in many families; however, it is more likely to be prevented in individuals who have established clear personal boundaries and possess the ability to adequately analyze situations, thereby preventing the development of chronic violence. Spouses often believe that they know and understand each other well; however, in reality, they may fail to understand their partner's inner world. Physical closeness in marriage does not automatically imply emotional intimacy. Achieving genuine closeness requires continuous effort, mutual interest, ongoing communication, and the ability to understand one another through dialogue. Such relationships develop between individuals who are open, free, and equal. V.A. Sysenko argues that the strength of family relationships is determined by the spouses' ability to bring joy to one another.

This strength is reflected in mutual affection, understanding, and the presence of positive emotions and laughter within the family. Family relationships and related issues are the subject of research in various disciplines, including psychology, pedagogy, sociology, demography, and economics. Scholars examine the dynamics of emotional relationships in marriage, the causes of loneliness and family disintegration, and the characteristics of family upbringing. The nature of the family as a complex social institution is determined not only by internal relationships but also by socio-economic, historical, national, and cultural conditions. The family evolves together with society while remaining one of its most stable and conservative elements.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Currently, changes in socio-cultural conditions are sharply intensifying the contradictions between family and extra-family relationships, a phenomenon often described as a "crisis of family values." Society is interested in a spiritually stable family capable of raising biologically and morally healthy children. The physical, social, and moral health of the younger generation represents the health of the entire nation. It is within the family that the foundations of a citizen's personality, value attitudes, and orientations are formed, corresponding to the needs of a socially just, legally regulated, and economically efficient society. Until recently, the family served as an organizing principle for the proper fulfillment of its core functions by the individual and acted as a source for acquiring labor skills and competencies that ensure successful social adaptation.

The study of the family, its place, and its role in the life of the individual and society is significant for several reasons. First, the history of human development demonstrates that no society has been able to function without the family, even in its most primitive forms, as an executor of specific social functions. Second, the family is the only social educational institution that reproduces individuals as carriers of social, cultural, and

ethnic information. Third, no society, state, or social institution—regardless of how humanely organized—can fully resolve the problem of psychological loneliness experienced by modern individuals. Successful socialization and identity formation require a stable rhythm of social relations characterized by long-term interpersonal interaction, oriented not toward individualistic or hedonistic aspirations, but toward the realization of higher social and spiritual values.

Social orphanhood, deviant behavior, adolescent suicide, difficulties in social and school adaptation, child prostitution, drug addiction, alcoholism, and crime constitute an incomplete list of asocial phenomena observed in contemporary society. The origins of these phenomena are closely connected with the condition of the family institution, while their elimination is possible only through the creation and strengthening of a full-fledged family structure. This practical and socially significant task determines the necessity of a comprehensive scientific and philosophical analysis of the family, including its modern evolution, thereby substantiating the relevance of the chosen topic. The family is a complex social institution that requires multidimensional analysis. The empirical study employed both qualitative and quantitative research methods. The subjective experiences, social attitudes, and mental states of women who had experienced violence were examined using questionnaires and semi-structured interviews. Levels of depression, anxiety, and self-esteem were assessed through standardized psychological diagnostic tools. Statistical methods were applied to analyze the collected data and to identify potential relationships between the level of social stigma and psycho-emotional disorders.

A happy family is a significant value that individuals strive to preserve. However, family well-being may be disrupted for various reasons, often stemming from differences in spouses' expectations regarding family life. For instance, a man may expect care, emotional support, intimacy, and attention from marriage, whereas a woman may prioritize childbirth, perceive marriage as self-sacrifice for the sake of children, and expect assistance and responsible behavior from her spouse. Mutual adaptation requires time and appropriate conditions. In the process of a woman's integration into a new family environment, the spouse often plays the role of a key mediator. It is commonly stated that no woman enters marriage with the intention of divorce; however, difficulties in adaptation to specific circumstances may lead to marital dissolution. In particular, A.V. Shabayeva conducted research on the socio-psychological aspects of leadership in marriage and demonstrated that the gender model of marriage in Muslim families tends to reinforce the husband's role within the family. Leadership relations between spouses are influenced by age, gender, ethnic background, and socio-economic conditions of family life. The findings of the present study confirm the assumptions proposed within the framework of stigmatization theory. Social stigma functions not only as external pressure but also negatively affects an individual's internal self-perception. The analysis indicates that combating violence requires not only legal measures but also systematic psychological and educational interventions aimed at transforming public consciousness.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, social stigma has a strong negative impact on the psycho-emotional state of women who have experienced domestic violence. Stigma increases depression, anxiety, and social withdrawal among women and complicates the rehabilitation process. The results of the study indicate the need to develop social support systems, expand psychological assistance, and implement programs aimed at reducing stigma in society.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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